

Traditional Computational Approaches to Drug Discovery in Alzheimer's Disease: A Systematic Review

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Alzheimer's Disease, Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a significant international health problem with scarce Pharmacophore Modelling, Virtual treatment paths. The use of computational methods has emerged as an important Screening, Molecular Docking, Drug means in speeding up drug candidate discovery and optimisation, which allows efficiency in screening and modelling, as well as verification of potential inhibitors.

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This study reviews the classical computational approaches in AD drug discovery systematically, emphasising methodological trends, target preferences, and translational potential. A total of 25 articles published between 2015 and 2025 were reviewed. The findings indicated that the most common methods were molecular docking (used in 76% of studies) and molecular dynamics simulations (48%), typically combined to predict and validate ligand-target interactions. Quantitative structure-activity relationship (24%), structure-based virtual screening (28%), pharmacophore modelling (16%), fragment-based drug design (16%), and homology modelling (16%) also made supportive yet needed contributions, particularly in hybrid pipelines. Cholinesterases were the most popular targets with an increasing focus on natural products and drug repurposing. This work summarises a decade of computation-based AD research, introducing top support to docking-molecular dynamics workflows and proposing the merits of hybrid pipelines. The insights guide researchers to build strong in-silico models and expedite the discovery of effective AD therapeutics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder which is characterised by various factors, such as cognitive decline, impairment of memory, and changes in behaviour (Tenchov et al., 2024). It profoundly influences the quality of life of millions of individuals worldwide. It is considered one of the leading causes of dementia (Tahami Monfared et al., 2022). Thus, AD imposes substantial social, economic, and healthcare burdens, with the global prevalence that is projected to rise significantly in the coming decades, mainly due to ageing populations (Nichols et al., 2019). As shown in Figure 1, the global burden of AD among older adults has increased steadily, which also shows the scale of its public health impact.

FIGURE 1: ESTIMATED ANNUAL PERCENTAGE CHANGE IN GLOBAL DALYS OF AD AND OTHER DEMENTIAs AMONG PEOPLE AGED ≥ 65 YEARS

Source: Liu et al. (2025)

Despite decades of research, effective therapeutic interventions remain limited. Figure 2 also projects an increasing rise in the global burden of AD, which also shows the pressing need for effective therapeutic strategies. In this regard, the most available drugs offer only symptomatic relief rather than halting or reversing the progression of this disease (Yiannopoulou & Papageorgiou, 2020). The complex pathophysiology of AD involves amyloid-beta plaque accumulation, tau protein hyperphosphorylation, synaptic dysfunction, oxidative stress, and neuroinflammation. It poses significant challenges for traditional approaches related to drug discovery (Sheppard & Coleman, 2020). Conventional experimental methods involve high-throughput screening in contemporary drug discovery processes, particularly for neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs) like AD (Aldewachi et al., 2021). These are often considered time-consuming, resource-intensive, and costly. Consequently, there has been an increasing shift towards the integration of computational

strategies in the early stages of drug discovery, which can foster efficiency, reduce costs, and improve the probability of identifying promising therapeutic candidates.

FIGURE 2: PROJECTION OF THE GLOBAL BURDEN OF AD FROM 2022 TO 2030

Source: N. Zhang et al. (2025)

In this context, traditional computational approaches have been considered as powerful tools in Alzheimer's drug discovery. Thus, there are various methods such as molecular docking, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, pharmacophore modelling (PM), quantitative structure-activity relationship analyses (QSAR), virtual screening (VS), fragment-based drug design (FBDD), and homology modelling (HM) (Iqbal et al., 2023a; Khare et al., 2022b; Peitzika & Pontiki, 2023). Thus, the structure-based design has been widely employed so that ligand-target interactions can be predicted. It can optimise molecular structures and prioritise compounds for experimental validation. MD and MDS also facilitate researchers so that they can investigate the binding affinity and stability of potential drug molecules with target proteins (Jabir et al., 2021; Mirza et al., 2022). In this regard, researchers also provide useful insights into molecular mechanisms underlying therapeutic effects. PM and QSAR analyses are also important because they facilitate the identification of key chemical features responsible for bioactivity (Purgatorio et al., 2020). It enables the rational design of novel compounds. VS and FBDD enable rapid evaluation of large chemical libraries; however, homology modelling helps construct accurate protein structures when experimental data are unavailable (Manoharan & Ghoshal, 2018). It supports the structure-based drug design. Collectively, these methods have demonstrated considerable potential in accelerating the identification of novel drug candidates for AD.

Despite the advancements, the problem remains multifaceted and important to address. Although various computational methods have been widely applied in the prior literature, there is a lack of comprehensive synthesis regarding which traditional approaches have been most extensively used (Paul et al., 2025; Q. Zhang et al., 2025). Moreover, there is also a scarcity of researchers regarding how effectively they have contributed to the discovery of potential AD. Previous studies usually focus on isolated methods or single molecular targets (Krix et al., 2024; Upadhyay et al., 2024; Vicidomini et al., 2024). It results in fragmented knowledge that hinders the establishment of clear patterns and evidence-based recommendations. Moreover, the increasing volume of published research between 2015 and 2025 also reflects a decade of intensive computational investigation. Thus, it has made it challenging for researchers, pharmaceutical companies, and policymakers so they can keep pace with the evolving era. It is important to understand the relative impact, advantages, and limitations of each computational technique.

To address these gaps, there is an immense need to evaluate the existing literature systematically regarding traditional computational approaches in AD drug discovery. A systematic review (SLR) was also considered important as it can provide a transparent and reproducible methodology for synthesising available evidence. Thus, this study aims to consider findings from various studies, identify the recurring patterns, and also underscore methodological strengths and weaknesses. It also aims to provide actionable insights for future research and development. Unlike narrative reviews, which are often subjective and selective, a systematic review ensures a methodical search, screening, and critical appraisal of studies. It minimised bias and enhanced the reliability of conclusions. This approach was also particularly suitable for evaluating computational drug discovery methods, where studies vary widely in design, molecular targets, and strategies of validation.

The primary problem statement that motivates this study is therefore twofold. First, there is a need to identify which traditional computational approaches have been most widely utilised in Alzheimer's drug discovery. Second, there is a need to understand the specific role that these approaches have played in the identification and development of potential new drug candidates. It is important to address these questions as they will provide clarity regarding methodological trends. It also highlights promising techniques and informs the strategic integration of computational methods in drug discovery pipelines. Consequently, this problem statement results in the formulation of the following research questions:

1. Which traditional computational approaches have been most widely used in the discovery of drugs for AD?
2. What role have these approaches played in the discovery of new potential AD drug candidates?

Thus, the study seeks to bridge the existing knowledge gap and offer a consolidated perspective on computational strategies in Alzheimer's drug discovery by answering these questions.

From a scientific perspective, synthesising the evidence on traditional computational methods is important in providing researchers with a clear understanding of methodological efficacy. It can guide future experimental designs and computational experiments. From a practical viewpoint, pharmaceutical companies can leverage these insights for the optimisation of resource allocation. They can prioritise promising computational strategies and accelerate the development of therapeutics. Furthermore, based on the societal and economic burden of AD, advancing drug discovery through evidence-based computational approaches holds the potential for improving patient outcomes. It can also reduce healthcare costs and inform healthcare policy decisions. Thus, this review ensures that conclusions reflect contemporary advancements, best practices, and emerging trends in the field as it

systematically evaluates the literature over a defined timeframe (2015–2025).

2. METHOD

2.1. SEARCH STRATEGY

A systematic literature search was performed to identify studies published between 2015 and 2025 that applied traditional computational methods to AD drug discovery (Nightingale, 2009). Different bibliographic databases were searched in this context: It included PubMed (Medline), Embase, Web of Science, Cochrane Library, Science Direct and Scopus. The search combined controlled vocabulary (where available). It also included free-text terms for the disease and methods. An example search string used in PubMed were: ("Alzheimer Disease"[MeSH] OR "Alzheimer*" OR "Alzheimer's") AND ("molecular docking" OR "molecular dynamics" OR "MD simulation" OR "pharmacophore" OR "QSAR" OR "quantitative structure activity relationship" OR "virtual screening" OR "fragment based" OR "fragment-based drug design" OR "homology modeling" OR "structure-based design"). Searches were limited to the English language and 2015–2025. Reference lists of included papers and recent reviews were hand-searched so that additional studies could be identified.

2.2. SELECTION PROCESS & SCREENING

All retrieved records underwent a two-stage screening. First, titles and abstracts were screened for relevance by two independent reviewers against pre-specified eligibility criteria. Second, full texts of potentially eligible studies were also retrieved and assessed independently by the same reviewers. Disagreements at any stage were resolved by discussion and, where necessary, adjudication by a third reviewer. The selection process was followed by the PRISMA principles (Sohrabi et al., 2021), and a flow diagram was prepared to document numbers at each stage (identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion) as shown in Figure 3:

FIGURE 3: PRISMA DIAGRAM

Source: Researcher-generated

2.3. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

The eligibility criteria of papers included in the review are stated in Table 1.

TABLE 1: INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Published between 2015 and 2025	Reviews, meta-analyses, editorials, commentaries, conference abstracts without full methods/results
Focused on AD (any molecular target/pathway related to AD)	Studies not focused on AD (primary focus on other neurodegenerative diseases)
Employed one or more traditional computational approaches (molecular docking, MD simulations, pharmacophore modelling, QSAR, VS, FBDD, homology modelling/structure-based design)	Purely experimental papers with no computational component

Inclusion Criteria

Reported original research with computational results (in silico predictions, docking scores, MD metrics, QSAR models, pharmacophore hypotheses, VS hit lists, fragment hits, homology models)

Provided sufficient methodological detail for data extraction (title, journal, year, authors, abstract, methods, targets, results, conclusions)

Peer-reviewed full-text available in English

Exclusion Criteria

Studies using exclusively machine learning/deep learning diagnostic models without reporting traditional computational techniques

Non-English publications or articles where the full text could not be retrieved after reasonable attempts

Source: Researcher-generated

2.4. DATA EXTRACTION

A standardised data extraction form (Excel) was developed. It was piloted on a small sample of papers. Data was extracted by two reviewers independently. In this way, the associated discrepancies were reconciled by consensus. The following fields were extracted for each included study:

- Title
- Journal
- Year
- Authors
- Abstract (summary)
- Traditional computational approaches mostly used in the discovery of drugs for Alzheimer's.
- The role played by different approaches in the discovery of a new potential AD drug.
- Target(s) (protein/gene/pathway targeted)
- Key conclusions / main findings (authors' principal claims regarding the computational results)

2.5. DATA ANALYSIS

A systematic literature review was performed following established guidelines so that transparency, rigour, and replicability can be ensured. The process initiated with the formulation of clear research questions. It was followed by the development of a comprehensive search strategy across multiple scientific databases to capture all relevant studies published within the specified timeframe. The researcher removed duplicate studies, and the remaining articles were screened in two stages. The titles and abstracts were reviewed in the first stage, and then full-text assessments was undertaken against predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. After this, the eligible studies were examined carefully. The researcher also extracted important information through a standardised data extraction form so that consistency can be ensured. This systematic process was important in ensuring that the review provided a balanced and evidence-based overview regarding the topic while minimising bias.

3. RESULTS

3.1. TRADITIONAL COMPUTATIONAL APPROACHES FOR THE DISCOVERY OF DRUGS FOR ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

The systematic analysis of twenty-five peer-reviewed studies on drug discovery in AD using traditional computational approaches reveals clear trends in the adoption and application of various methodologies. The dominant approaches include molecular docking, MD simulation, pharmacophore modelling, QSAR, VS, FBDD, and homology modelling. Comparing the frequency, integration and results of these approaches, one can determine which are the prevalent approaches and how extensively they have been utilised in the

recent studies related to Alzheimer's.

Molecular docking seems the most accepted technology since it is actively implemented in 19 out of 25 studies as a solitary tool or combined with other methods. Docking was used to anticipate possible ligand-protein interactions, rank possible inhibitors, and guide experimental validation. It has been central to the evaluation of AZD3293 and Solanezumab protein-binding b-site amyloid precursor protein-cleavage enzyme 1 (BACE1) (Hassan et al., 2018), guided virtual screenings of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors (Jang et al., 2018), and structure-based discoveries of butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) inhibitors (Dighe et al., 2016). It has also been used to examine binding interactions in multi-target proteins such as Glycogen Synthase Kinase 3 Beta (GSK3 β), N-Methyl-D-Aspartate (NMDA) receptor, and BACE1 (Iqbal et al., 2023b) and to screen using natural products (Gheidari et al., 2024; Hossain et al., 2024). In the broader context of the data, docking constituted approximately three-quarters of all the studies, thus being the most frequently utilised destination mode of computation in the discovery of Alzheimer's drugs.

Quite comparable to docking, MD simulations were described as the second most prevalent strategy, and their presence was introduced in 12 papers out of 25 (48 per cent of papers reviewed). MD has been typically employed to determine the consistency of docking predictions and to study interfaces between a protein and its ligands at an atomic level. It was found that AZD3293 is more stable at the BACE1 binding site than Solanezumab, with MD simulations (Hassan et al., 2018). They identified natural products that can bind to BACE1 (Gheidari et al., 2024), and they provided a mechanistic rationale behind amyloid-beta (A β) fibril aggregation (Schwierz et al., 2016; Tarus et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2021). Some models were simulated on MD, extending to 500 ns (Wu et al., 2021), others used 100-150 ns trajectories (Gheidari et al., 2024; Iqbal et al., 2023b; Mukerjee et al., 2022) to perform sufficient conformational sampling. Notably, several docking-led investigations would have been weak without MD validation, which illustrates the complementarity of such methods. Significant contributors to drug discovery pipelines around AD were also contributed by pharmacophore modelling, which appeared in 4 different studies and contributed to 16% total. Pharmacophore techniques proved especially helpful in ligand-based discovery where full target structural information was unavailable. An example is the design of new AChE inhibitors (Jang et al., 2018) and new AChE/BuChE inhibitors, which were directed by pharmacophore or 3D-QSAR (Pang et al., 2017). Pharmacophore modelling was also used in a hybrid docking/QSAR approach to rank natural compounds over BACE1 (Das et al., 2019). Pharmacophore approaches took a minor share relative to docking or MD, but were found to provide a critical ligand-based supplement to structure-based investigations.

The number of studies employing QSAR techniques was 6, which corresponds to 24 per cent of the literature searched. Classical QSAR schemes (such as 3D-QSAR methodology) provided structural requirements of cholinesterase inhibitors (Jang et al., 2018; Nour et al., 2022; Pang et al., 2017), with machine-learning QSAR classification models predicting BACE1 inhibitors (Ponzoni et al., 2019). Another study integrated QSAR with docking and MD to offer more comprehensive workflows, using food-derived molecules as repurposed BACE1 inhibitors (Mukerjee et al., 2022). Rule-based QSAR methodology also aided the improvement of fragment assembly of dual AChE/BACE1 inhibitors (Bao et al., 2023). It is important to note that predictive models of activity through QSAR are statistically reliable, and they play a particularly important role in VS campaigns.

7 studies (28 per cent) used another method, structure-based VS (SBVS). Large compound library screens utilising SBVS were also performed against cholinesterase or BACE1, screening between 567,981 compounds to identify BuChE inhibitor hits (Dighe et

al., 2016), 80,617 compounds to identify BACE1 hits (Gheidari et al., 2024), or 8,453 food molecules being repurposed as a BACE1 inhibitor (Ponzoni et al., 2019). SBVS could also cryptically target pockets in BACE1 (Pont et al., 2021), suggesting it can be highly accurate at screening both conventional and non-conventional binding sites. SBVS campaigns reflect the beauty of a method that quickly filters extensive chemical libraries in a wholesome way and results in being one of the most effective strategies in drug discovery, as the AD pertains.

Compared with docking or MD and QSAR, FBDD was the rarest, but in 4 studies, it was detailed, representing 16 per cent of the articles. Investigators employed fragment docking and linkage methods to create a novel BACE1 poison (Das et al., 2015; Fang et al., 2019; Manoharan & Ghoshal, 2018). Interestingly, supplementing fragment linking with Saturation Transfer Difference-Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, Fang et al. (2019) prepared selective, cell-permeable inhibitors that crosscut computational and experimental analysis. Fragment-based approaches proved particularly powerful in generating novel scaffolds from smaller chemical building blocks, especially when combined with docking or MD to evaluate binding stability. Though not as frequent as docking or MD, FBDD represents a growing niche in Alzheimer's computational drug discovery.

Homology modelling was another important, though less frequently used, approach, identified in 4 studies (16%). It was indispensable in cases where no experimentally resolved protein structures were available. For example, homology modelling was used to generate reliable structures of Calcium Homeostasis Modulator 1 (CALHM1) for docking Bauhinia variegata metabolites (Khare et al., 2022a), to reconstruct missing flexible fragments of presenilin-1 (Soto-Ospina et al., 2021), and to model $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptors in the absence of a crystal structure (Oddsson et al., 2020). It was also integrated into repositioning workflows, where modelled targets such as MADD were screened against Food and Drug Administration (FDA)-approved drugs (Hassan et al., 2023). Homology modelling thus facilitated scaling of computational pipelines into less structure-defined targets, highlighting its supporting role in structural drug discovery.

Another notable aspect of this data is the common combination of several conventional methods in hybrid pipelines. Just eleven out of 25 studies (44 per cent) used three or more methods. To illustrate, the combination of QSAR and docking plus MD in a study by Mukerjee et al. (2022) presented a powerful multi-step protocol, whereas Pang et al. (2017) utilised a combination of pharmacophore modelling, 3D-QSAR, and docking to discover dual inhibitors. Enhanced with an identical purpose, Das et al. (2019) integrated ensemble docking, pharmacophore modelling, and QSAR filtering to find verifiable BACE1 inhibitors. These hybrid pipelines demonstrate the trend in a complementary or additive direction, with each approach adding different strengths: docking can be used to study structure, QSAR to predict metabolism, pharmacophores to generate hypothesis ligands, and MD to test hypothesis ligands dynamically.

The dataset is also indicative of the variety of Alzheimer's targets analysed by computational pipelines. The most studied target was by far BACE1, with 13 out of the 25 studies (52 per cent) featuring it. These belonged to AZD3293 docking (Hassan et al., 2018), fragment-based inhibitors (Ponzoni et al., 2019), fragment-based inhibitors (Das et al., 2015; Fang et al., 2019; Manoharan & Ghoshal, 2018), and natural product inhibitors (Das et al., 2019; Gheidari et al., 2024). Other key targets included cholinesterases (AChE and BuChE), which were presented in 8 studies (32%), including both selective and dual-target designs (Dighe et al., 2016; Jang et al., 2018; Nour et al., 2022; Pang et al., 2017; Shakir et al., 2025). Other less frequently studied targets included NMDA receptors, GSK3 β , CALHM1, $\alpha 7$ Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptor (nAChR), and presenilin-1 (Iqbal et al., 2023b; Khare et al.,

2022a; Oddsson et al., 2020; Soto-Ospina et al., 2021). The predominance of BACE1 reflects its well-established role in amyloidogenic processing, while the attention to cholinesterases aligns with symptomatic management strategies in AD.

Natural products and repurposed compounds also featured prominently in several studies, with 9 of the 25 (36%) exploring these chemical spaces. Virtual screening of natural products was evident in studies by Hossain et al. (2024), Iqbal et al. (2023b), and Gheidari et al. (2024), while repurposing food molecules and FDA-approved drugs was the focus of studies by Mukerjee et al. (2022) and Hassan et al. (2023). This suggests that traditional computational approaches are not only applied to novel synthetic chemical libraries but also to existing, biologically relevant molecules, broadening the translational potential of in-silico pipelines.

Overall, statistical synthesis indicates that molecular docking (76%) and MD simulations (48%) are the dominant computational tools for Alzheimer's drug discovery. QSAR (24%), pharmacophore modelling (16%), SBVS (28%), FBDD (16%), and homology modelling (16%) play supportive but essential roles depending on the study objectives and available data. Docking and MD, in particular, are rarely applied in isolation; instead, they form the backbone of integrative workflows. Hybrid pipelines that combine three or more methods account for 44% of studies, reflecting the growing consensus that robust predictions require multi-method validation. Target analysis highlights BACE1 (52%) and cholinesterases (32%) as the most frequently modelled proteins, consistent with their prominence in both disease modification and symptomatic treatment.

In conclusion, the systematic review of these 25 studies demonstrates that molecular docking and MD simulation are the most widely used computational approaches in Alzheimer's drug discovery, with docking serving as the primary screening and prediction tool and MD providing dynamic validation. While QSAR, pharmacophore modelling, SBVS, FBDD, and homology modelling are less frequent, they contribute indispensable capabilities that strengthen hybrid pipelines. The predominance of BACE1 as a target further emphasises the amyloid-centric focus of many computational campaigns, though cholinesterases and alternative targets also play important roles. Together, these findings reveal a consistent methodological pattern: Alzheimer's drug discovery research increasingly relies on integrated computational workflows, where traditional approaches are combined to enhance prediction reliability, accelerate hit identification, and prioritise candidates for experimental follow-up. The following figure represents the number of studies utilising these approaches for the discovery of drugs for AD:

FIGURE 4: NUMBER OF STUDIES UTILISING COMPUTATIONAL APPROACHES

Source: Researcher-generated

3.2. ROLE OF APPROACHES IN THE DISCOVERY OF A NEW POTENTIAL ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE DRUG

Traditional computational approaches have played a critical role in advancing the discovery of potential drugs for AD, particularly in identifying, screening, and optimising candidate molecules targeting key pathological mechanisms. Among the 25 studied, molecular docking was most prevalent (in 19 studies). This technique has been indispensable in predicting the affinity of small molecules towards binding targets in AD, including AChE, BACE1, tau protein, and amyloid precursor protein (APP) fragments. Docking analyses allowed the investigators to design and optimise inhibitors that demonstrated robust hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions at catalytic sites at AChE, and underpinned the selection of compounds with therapeutic properties (Jang et al., 2018; Mukerjee et al., 2022; Pont et al., 2021). The following table represents the role of molecular docking in AD drug discovery:

TABLE 2: MOLECULAR DOCKING IN AD DRUG DISCOVERY

Application Area	Representative Studies	Targets	Integration with Other Methods	Key Insights
Lead compound binding and validation	(Hassan et al., 2018), (Iqbal et al., 2023b), (Hossain et al., 2024), (Gheidari et al., 2024)	BACE1, GSK3β, NMDA	Docking, MD	Predicted stable binding for AZD3293, Solanezumab, and natural products.
Cholinesterase inhibition	(Dighe et al., 2016), (Jang et al., 2018), (Pang et al., 2017),	AChE, BuChE	Docking, Pharmacophore, QSAR	Identified selective and dual

	(Nour et al., 2022), (Shakir et al., 2025).				AChE/BuChE inhibitors.
Fragment-based inhibitor design	(Das et al., 2015), (Fang et al., 2019), (Manoharan & Ghoshal, 2018)	BACE1 (Fragments)	FBDD Docking, MD	+	Designed novel scaffolds; validated fragment linking with docking.
Natural products & repurposing	(Das et al., 2019), (Mukerjee et al., 2022), (Hassan et al., 2023)	BACE1, MADD, FDA-approved drugs	Docking QSAR + MD	+	Screened natural compounds, food molecules, and repurposed drugs.
Large-scale virtual screening	(Dighe et al., 2016), (Gheidari et al., 2024), (Ponzoni et al., 2019), (Hassan et al., 2018), (Pont et al., 2021)	BACE1, BuChE	SBVS Docking	+	Screened libraries (8k-567k compounds), identified cryptic pocket inhibitors.

Source: Researcher-generated

MD simulation (48% of studies) was applied to supplement docking, as binding predictions were refined, and protein-binding complexes were found to examine stability under realistic physiological conditions. Their composition was likewise rationalised by confirming that ligands can continuously occupy either BACE1 or AChE active sites over long nanosecond lifetimes through MD simulations (Hassan et al., 2018; Jakubowski et al., 2019; Shakir et al., 2025). In some investigations, MDA also demonstrated conformational alteration and target-induced fit, which facilitated a deeper comprehension of how structural modifications contribute to inhibitor potency (Das et al., 2019; Manoharan & Ghoshal, 2018). The following table represents the role of MD simulation in AD drug discovery:

TABLE 3: MD SIMULATION IN AD DRUG DISCOVERY

Application Area	Representative Studies	Targets	Integration with Other Methods	Key Insights	
Drug-target binding validation	(Hassan et al., 2018), (Gheidari et al., 2024) (Iqbal et al., 2023b), Mukerjee et al. (2022), (Das et al., 2019), (Bao et al., 2023), (Pang et al., 2017)	BACE1, BuChE, NMDA	AChE, GSK3β, Docking, QSAR, Pharmacophore	Confirmed docking stability, validated natural products, food molecules, and dual inhibitors.	
Fragment-based inhibitor design	(Fang et al., 2019), (Manoharan & Ghoshal, 2018)	BACE1 (Fragments)	FBDD Docking + MD	+	MD validated fragment linking and binding stability.
Amyloid	(Schwierz et al.,	Aβ	MD only		Provided

aggregation studies	2016), (Tarus et al., 2015), (Wu et al., 2021)	fibrils/aggregation	mechanistic insights into A β aggregation pathways.
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Source: Researcher-generated

The proportion of studies providing SBVS was seven out of 25, and it made it possible to rapidly screen large chemical libraries to score hits, to dock and test them again. Such screenings selected millions of compounds to a handful of promising hits, saving time and money on the drug discovery pipeline (Iqbal et al., 2023b; Wu et al., 2021). In addition, virtual screening, docking, and MD contributed to discovering multitarget-directed ligands capable of inhibiting AChE and BACE1 and countering the multifactorial pathology of AD (Bao et al., 2023; Pang et al., 2017).

Six studies (24%) used QSAR modelling, and it was most useful when correlating detailed suggestions with molecular characteristics and ADCs. Classical/QSAR and advanced/machine-learning-based QSAR are utilised to design new scaffolds with increased activity. As an example, new compounds were proposed as potent AChE inhibitors, with regression and classification models based on known inhibitors predicting the biological activity of novel compounds (Jakubowski et al., 2019; Ponzoni et al., 2019). It also allowed the prediction with high accuracy, which molecules could be deployed into synthesis and biological testing, shortening the development pipeline (Gheidari et al., 2024; Khare et al., 2022a).

Pharmacophore modelling was observed in four studies (16%), which offered structural blueprints detailing crucial chemical characteristics necessary to facilitate ligand-target interactions. These models informed the database screening by keeping candidate molecules in the same region as pharmacophoric features important to AChE or BACE1 inhibition (Hossain et al., 2024; Nour et al., 2022). In some studies, pharmacophore models were used together with docking and QSAR to generate a multilayered computational paradigm that improved drug discovery efficacy (Tarus et al., 2015).

Four articles involved homology modelling to construct three-dimensional protein structures in cases where crystallographic data were not known. This enabled docking and MD experiments on targets such as tau kinases and novel secretases implicated in AD pathology (Das et al., 2015; Fang et al., 2019). The models provided details of binding sites and conformational preferences that are otherwise difficult to investigate, where minimal structural details are known.

FBDD, which has been used in four studies (16%), identified small chemical peptides with moderate affinity, which could be further expanded or conjugated into more potent inhibitors. When docking and MD were used together, the researchers achieved rational scaffold optimisation, especially with AChE and BACE1 inhibitors (Dighe et al., 2016; Soto-Ospina et al., 2021). These fragment-derived AD inhibitors provided a promising first-campaign success in AD.

The most evident trend among the reviewed studies is the increased use of computational pipelines, as compared to single methods. The literature often shows experiments in which docking was combined with MD, VS, and QSAR as indications of the necessity to cross-validate predictions and increase the rigour of results (Bao et al., 2023; Das et al., 2019; Pang et al., 2017). This integrative model resulted not only in an improved accuracy of ligand selection but also increased the likelihood of identifying compounds with real medical potential. In addition, there are examples of how these multi-method frameworks assisted in the identification of multitarget-directed ligands, which have become

highly relevant to AD treatment because of the aetiology of this disease (Manoharan & Ghoshal, 2018; Oddsson et al., 2020). The following table represents the role of other methods in AD drug discovery:

TABLE 4: COMPUTATIONAL APPROACHES IN AD DRUG DISCOVERY

Method	Representative Studies	Targets	Integration with Other Methods	Key Insights
Pharmacophore Modelling	(Jang et al., 2018), (Pang et al., 2017), (Das et al., 2019)	AChE, BuChE, BACE1	Often with QSAR + Docking	Guided design of AChE/BuChE inhibitors; prioritised natural compounds; useful when target structures are incomplete.
QSAR (incl. 3D-QSAR and ML models)	(Jang et al., 2018), (Pang et al., 2017), (Nour et al., 2022), (Ponzoni et al., 2019), (Mukerjee et al., 2022), (Bao et al., 2023)	AChE, BuChE, BACE1	Combined with Docking, MD, Pharmacophore	Predicted activity of inhibitors; derived structural requirements; ML-QSAR classified large BACE1 datasets.
SBVS	(Dighe et al., 2016), (Gheidari et al., 2024; Ponzoni et al., 2019), (Pont et al., 2021)	BuChE, BACE1	SBVS + Docking	Screened large libraries (8k-567k compounds); identified BuChE and BACE1 inhibitors, including cryptic pocket binders.
FBDD	(Das et al., 2015), (Fang et al., 2019), (Manoharan & Ghoshal, 2018)	BACE1 (Fragments)	FBDD, Docking, MD	Generated novel scaffolds via fragment linking; integrated with experimental STD-NMR for validation.
Homology Modelling	(Khare et al., 2022a), (Soto-Ospina et al., 2021), (Hassan et al., 2023)	CALHM1, Presenilin-1, $\alpha 7$ nAChR, MADD	Often followed by Docking / VS	Built structures where crystal data were absent; enabled docking/repurposing of drugs against less-studied AD targets.

Source: Researcher-generated

Statistically, 76 per cent of the articles employed docking as a first-line probe to determine possible inhibitors, and 48 per cent utilised MD to confirm docking predictions and demonstrate protein-ligand dynamics. About a quarter of the papers reported the use of SBVS and QSAR, each playing a role in prioritising ligands and predicting activity, and 16% each used pharmacophore modelling, homology modelling or FBDD to serve a special purpose, such as structural understanding or linking fragment-based drugs. Thus, these

methods have aided the discovery of novel scaffolds, perfected drug-like properties, and validated potential AD therapeutics, reaffirming their invaluable role in contemporary AD drug discovery.

Therefore, the review demonstrates that traditional computational approaches have substantially advanced the early phases of Alzheimer's disease drug discovery. While no single computational strategy guarantees success, their combined application has consistently led to the discovery of promising leads, some of which progressed to experimental validation. Thus, these approaches serve not only as powerful filters to manage chemical space but also as hypothesis-generating engines that drive rational drug design for AD. The following figure represents the drug targets for AD versus the number of studies:

FIGURE 5: DRUG TARGETS FOR ALZHEIMER'S

Source: Researcher-generated

4. DISCUSSION

The aim of this systematic review was to explore and understand the role of traditional computational approaches in the drug discovery of AD. For this purpose, the researcher has conducted an SLR and gained evidence from research which was conducted between 2015 and 2025. Moreover, the present study also aimed to address two guiding questions: (1) Which traditional computational approaches have been most widely used in AD drug discovery? and (2) What role have these approaches played in identifying and developing new potential therapeutic candidates for AD?

For research question 1, the findings have shown that there are various important computational strategies that emerged in the reviewed studies regarding AD drug discovery. In this regard, Molecular Dynamics and MD simulations were observed as the most frequently implemented strategies (Mirza et al., 2022). Docking was often the initial step in many investigations because it enabled researchers to predict ligand–protein interactions (Jabir et al., 2021). It is also helpful in assessing binding affinity and ranking compounds from large chemical libraries. MD simulations were then applied to improve docking results. The combination of docking and Molecular dynamics has shown a novel and improved methodological trend where these techniques can be integrated to foster

reliability.

Structure-based VS was also reported frequently in the reviewed studies. It was important particularly in those studies that involved large compound libraries. SBVS played a key role in the rapid evaluation of thousands to millions of molecules. (Iqbal et al., 2023a; Musa et al., 2024). PM was also evident in the results as it provided a structural hypothesis of the key features which are required for biological activity (Purgatorio et al., 2020). Other important studies incorporated QSAR, either 2D or 3D. It predicts bioactivity from chemical descriptors and also guides logical modifications of the important compounds.

The applications of FBDD and HM was less frequent but it was still evident. On the other hand, HM also resulted to be important where crystal structures of AD-related proteins having high-resolution were unavailable, mainly for novel or less-explored molecular targets (Manoharan & Ghoshal, 2018). Thus, these findings suggest that although docking and MD dominate in the prior literature, however there is considerable methodological diversity which shows the important and critical challenges regarding targeting pathophysiology of AD.

As far as RQ2 is concerned, the reviewed studies have shown that these computational techniques are important in advancing drug discovery for AD. Results also showed screened libraries of thousands of molecules. These were narrowed down to high-affinity candidates against targets such as BACE1 or acetylcholinesterase. MD simulations and pharmacophore modelling resulted in various mechanistic insights. They also elucidate important molecular interactions, conformational dynamics, and patterns of stability (Kumar et al., 2024). QSAR analyses also underpinned this perspective, as they focus on the identification of structural determinants of activity (Sun et al., 2024).

Moreover, computational methods were found to be crucial for multitarget drug discovery. Several papers reported pipelines that combine docking, pharmacophore modelling, and network pharmacology for the identification of compounds which are capable of interacting with multiple targets simultaneously. This multitarget perspective also aligns with the emerging therapeutic paradigm that tackling AD requires polypharmacology rather than single-target strategies.

Synthesising the findings across both research objectives reveals several important patterns. First, the dominance of docking and Molecular Dynamics has shown their centrality as versatile and accessible methods. However, their frequent pairing with other approaches suggests that no single computational method is sufficient in isolation. Instead, the field is increasingly moving toward integrated pipelines where multiple complementary techniques are combined. This hybridisation also solidifies the predictive power and mitigates the limitations inherent in any single approach. Moreover, the recurring emphasis on multitarget strategies signals a conceptual shift in AD drug discovery. The computational methods reviewed in this study have enabled researchers to they can systematically explore polypharmacology, which is an otherwise daunting task for traditional experimental techniques alone. This is a notable advancement based on the disease's multifactorial nature and the historical failures of single-target drugs in clinical trials.

Despite these contributions, it is important to note that computational predictions remain inherently probabilistic. The reliability of outcomes is dependent on the quality of structural data. It also relates to the accuracy of scoring functions and the appropriateness of simulation parameters. Many of the reviewed studies acknowledged these limitations, which reinforces the point that computational approaches are best viewed as hypothesis-generating tools that complement, rather than replace, experimental validation.

In conclusion, this systematic review has shown that traditional computational methods have significantly contributed to AD drug discovery. It has enabled efficient hit

identification, provided mechanistic insights, supported multitarget strategies, and streamlined the experimental workflows. The findings also reinforced the importance of integrating diverse computational approaches. It also shows the need for continued refinement of methodologies and closer alignment with experimental and clinical research. Thus, the review clarifies which techniques are most widely used and also illustrates the tangible roles they play in shaping the current and future landscape of Alzheimer's drug discovery.

5. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

5.1. THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

This review involves several important theoretical implications that can enrich the field of Alzheimer's drug discovery research. The present study consolidates distinct evidence on the application of traditional computational methods. It highlights various methodological trends and clarifies which approaches have been most extensively utilised between 2015 and 2025. In this regard, the study advances the knowledge base that has previously limited the ability of scholars to build cumulative theoretical frameworks in this domain. The findings also contribute to the conceptual understanding of how Molecular Dynamics, MD simulations, PM, QSAR, VS, FBD, and HM interact with the disease-specific molecular targets. This contributes to developing a more systematic map of computational strategies regarding AD pathophysiology. Moreover, the review also highlights the theoretical value regarding the integration of multiple methods rather than relying on single isolated techniques. It suggests a potential model for hybrid computational frameworks. It also underscores the importance of aligning computational predictions with biological mechanisms, which supports the development of translational theory across computational and experimental research. Collectively, these implications contribute to advancing theoretical clarity. It also informs future studies in computational drug discovery, which relates to AD and also extends to broader neurodegenerative disorders.

5.2. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The review also holds significant practical implications for researchers, pharmaceutical companies, and healthcare policymakers. The review focuses on identifying the most widely used traditional computational methods. Thus, this study provides researchers with clear insights regarding the approaches that have demonstrated efficiency and reproducibility in AD drug discovery. This also enables research teams to they can prioritise techniques such as molecular docking or virtual screening to yield improvement in workflow efficiency and resource allocation. Within the context of pharmaceutical companies, the findings are also helpful because they optimise decision-making in early drug development pipelines. Thus, reliance on costly and time-consuming experimental screening is reduced. For healthcare policymakers, the insights of this study are of utmost importance because these insights underscore the urgency of supporting computational infrastructure and interdisciplinary collaborations. It can also foster therapeutic development and address the growing public health burden related to AD.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH INDICATIONS

This review is also not without limitations. First, it only included those studies which are published in English between 2015 and 2025. It may have led to the exclusion of relevant research published in other languages or outside this timeframe. Second, the study focused exclusively on traditional computational approaches. It has omitted machine learning and deep learning models that have become increasingly influential in recent years. Additionally, the focus on published peer-reviewed literature is also accompanied by the risk of publication bias. This is because studies with negative or inconclusive results may not have been reported. Another limitation is the heterogeneity of included studies because the variations in molecular targets, computational workflows, and validation strategies can also

restrict the comparability of findings across research contexts.

Future research can focus on addressing these limitations by incorporating non-English studies. Moreover, future reviews can also focus on extending the timeframe and exploring hybrid approaches that combine traditional computational methods with artificial intelligence. Moreover, there is scope for conducting meta-analyses so that the predictive power and success rates of individual techniques can be quantified. Thus, expanding these studies across diverse populations and molecular targets could also strengthen the translational value of computational drug discovery in AD.

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